

A Study of Methods and Techniques to Manage the Occupational Stress Among the Bank Employees of Meerut Region

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Abstract

Stress on individuals ranges from personal day-to-day life to their organizational activities. Stress is the spice of life and the absence of stress makes life dull, monotonous and spiritless. Workplace stress has been shown to have a detrimental effect on the health and wellbeing of employees, as well as a negative impact on workplace productivity and profits. Stress may cause within organizational context and outside. The job nature of banking employees is very tedious as it involves the direct customer interaction in all levels. There are several self-help remedies which are used to produce effective techniques for coping with stress. So it should be considered an efficient way of improving organizational profitability and reducing costs through lowering rates of absenteeism and turnover. Because employees spend roughly one third of their lives working in an organization, the sound mental health of employees is of paramount importance. The management takes necessary initiatives to overcome the disastrous effect of occupational stress. Managing stress will improve the chances of achieving sustainable productivity levels. Stress management should be included as one of the top agendas in modern day society.

Keywords: Stress, Banking employees, Workplace Stress, Productivity, Stress Management

Classification-JEL : G21, J24, J81.

1. INTRODUCTION

Banking industry plays important role in the developing the country's economy is not an exceptional one. The job nature of banking employees is very tedious as it involves the direct customer interaction in all levels. Job stress has become one of the most critical health issues in the modern world. Nevertheless, the effect of job stress is not on the part of the employee only since the organization also expects to experience the

unfavorable outcome. Stress will give a variety of consequences and the effect will different among each individual. The experience of stress is related with feeling of increasing distress, which leads to anxiety and depression. People in stress may find difficult to make decision, to think logically and to concentrate. Its job conditions are unique, its demands are tedious and banks are emphasizing on human resources not out of chance or compassion but out of sheer compulsion. The technological

advancements put a lot of pressure on employee and organizations, demanding more immediate and direct changes across all functionalities. Stress management should be included as one of the top agendas in modern day society.

There is no general objective on the rating of satisfaction, since it is rather subjective and depends on individual motivation and how employees personally perceive their labour conditions. One of the part criteria for satisfaction level besides incentives or responsibility is the participation of the employees. Hence, the characteristics of satisfaction, the participation approaches cannot be separated beneficial and unfavorable. Some of the employees may prefer it while others employees may desire doing a routine job. By doing their favors job, it can boost the companies productivity. The success of organization is relying on the employee satisfaction on their job. Thus, it requires in enhancing the employee satisfaction is a critical part since it is become an input towards the success of an organization. In the recent surroundings, the employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction can give the major impact directly towards the achievement of the organization. From the employees standpoint, encouraging working environment coupled with others incentives such as increment in salary and frequent training will uplift the organization to the success. Hence, it appears reasonable to state that understanding of employee role is extremely important for the success of modern organization.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE RESEARCH PAPER

To analyze the methods and techniques to manages occupational stress among bank employees.

Sampling Design

The researcher conducts a brief primary data collection on a basis of area and

convenience sampling from ICICI Bank of Meerut Region.

**TABLE 1
ICICI BANK**

S. No.	Branch Name	No. of Respondents
1.	ICICI Bank, Kankerkhhera (Adarsh Nagar)	8
2.	ICICI Bank, Meerut (Rajlok)	12
3.	ICICI Bank, Baghpat Road (Avas Vikas Compound)	6
4.	ICICI Bank, Begum Bridge Road (City Plaza)	8
5.	ICICI Bank, Delhi Road (Opp. Rani Mill)	8
6.	ICICI Bank, Garh Road (BDS Complex)	6
7.	ICICI Bank, Jain Nagar	6
8.	ICICI Bank, Mawana (Moti Palace)	5
9.	ICICI Bank, Mawana Road (Trupati Garden)	6
10.	ICICI Bank, Pallavpuram, Phase-1	6
11.	ICICI Bank, Westend Road	8
12.	ICICI Bank, Hapur Road (Shivpuri)	8
13.	ICICI Bank, Delhi Road (Shatabdi Nagar)	7
14.	ICICI Bank, Vedvyaspuri (NH58-Ghat)	6
	Total Respondents	100

3. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Fig. 1

Employee Assistance Programme plays a vital role in managing employee stress

Out of 100 employees, 29 are strongly agreed, 43 are Agree, 4 are Neutral, 16 are Disagree and 8 are strongly disagreed. Employees cited that these programmes helps in managing personal problems, dealing with family problems, dealing with health problems, and dealing with other kind of personal and family stresses.

Fig. 2

Career planning and counseling plays a vital role in managing employee stress

Out of 100 employees, 23 are strongly agreed, 37 are Agree, 6 are Neutral, 21 are Disagree and 13 are strongly disagreed. Employees cited that career planning and counseling help the employees to obtain professional advice regarding career paths that would help them to achieve personal goals.

Fig. 3

Relationship with co-employees plays a vital role in managing employee stress

Out of 100 employees, 28 are strongly agreed, 39 are Agree, 5 are Neutral, 18 are Disagree and 10 are strongly disagreed. Employees cited that organizations do control and understand all means to influence job

characteristics, yet they obviously have limited power over the level of social support co-employees provide to each other.

Fig. 4

Salary and fringe benefits plays a vital role in managing employee stress

Out of 100 employees, 32 are strongly agreed, 46 are Agree, 2 are Neutral, 13 are Disagree and 7 are strongly disagreed. Employees cited that these benefits may lead to motivation, feeling sense of responsibility and utilizing maximum capability at the work. Such a phenomenon helps in reducing stress.

4. CONCLUSION

Job stress has become one of the most critical health issues in the modern world. Nevertheless, the effect of job stress is not on the part of the employee only since the organization also expects to experience the unfavorable outcome. Stress will give a variety of consequences and the effect will different among each individual. The experience of stress is related with feeling of increasing distress, which leads to anxiety and depression. People in stress may find difficult to make decision, to think logically and to concentrate.

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